

Mediation Effect of Job Satisfaction between Transactional Leadership and Employee Performance

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ABSTRACT: The basis for conducting this study was to investigate the effect of transactional leadership behaviour on employee performance as well as the role job satisfaction played as a mediating variable in the relationship between transactional leadership style and employee performance. Evidence of previous studies that investigated how transactional leadership affected employee performance were contained in the literature. However, studies that indicated the role job satisfaction played in the transactional leadership-employee performance relationship were scanty. This necessitated conducting the study to determine the mediating effect of job satisfaction between predictor and outcome variables.

A survey research design was the basis for carrying out the study. Data were collected on a scale that ranged from strongly disagree 1, to strongly agree, 4. Data collection was from a random sample of 226 employees of a food and beverage manufacturing company in Lagos State, Nigeria. Inferential statistics involving simple and multiple regression was the basis for data analyses.

The findings indicated that job satisfaction partially mediated the relationship between transactional leadership style and employee performance; the effect of transactional leadership on employee performance was positive as well as the effect of transactional leadership on job satisfaction. However, there was insignificant positive effect of job satisfaction on performance.

The conclusion of the study stated that transactional leadership was a good predictor of employee performance. It was also indicated that the management of the studied company should ensure the availability of factors that promote job satisfaction and give more attention to ensuring the adequacy of rewards for attaining goals in a transactional relationship with employees as a means of boosting performance.

KEYWORDS: Employee performance, job satisfaction, mediation effect, transactional leadership.

INTRODUCTION

Transactional leadership is leadership that rewards followers on the basis of accomplished goals so that failure to accomplish goals results in withholding rewards. Studies that investigated the influence of transactional leadership on performance include: Obiwuru et al. (2011), Koech and Namusonge (2012), Dele et al. (2015), Arsawan et al. (2017), and Hoxha, (2019). However, the literature suggested the need for more studies to investigate the mediating effect of job satisfaction in the relationship between transactional leadership and employee performance. Job satisfaction measures the contentment of employees with regard to the job they do, the work environment, financial and non-financial rewards, leadership styles, and so on.. Transactional leaders set work goals for accomplishment. The process of working to achieve goals is characterised by various activities, experiences, and conditions. For this reason, it was necessary to assess how leadership behaviour affected employee performance and the role job satisfaction played in the transactional leadership-employee performance relationship. This assessment was hinged on the assumption that, being a goal-oriented and contingent-reward leadership style, organisations carrying out business in competitive environments need to avoid or reduce to the smallest levels, the consequences of having employees that experience poor job satisfaction.

The broad objective of this study was to assess the mediation effect of job satisfaction between transactional leadership style and employee performance. The specific objectives were to determine the effect of transactional leadership style on employee performance; and to examine the effect of transactional leadership on job satisfaction.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

The following hypotheses were tested for rejection or acceptance:

H₀1: Transactional leadership style has no significant effect on employee performance

H₀2: Transactional leadership style has no significant effect on job satisfaction

H₀3: Job satisfaction has no mediating effect between transactional leadership style and employee performance

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of job satisfaction mediating between transactional leadership style and employee performance

Source: Author, 2024

MODEL OF THE STUDY

$$EP = \alpha + \beta_1 TS + \epsilon \quad \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$JS = \alpha + \beta_2 TS + \epsilon \quad \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$$EP = \alpha + \beta_3 TS + \beta_4 JS + \epsilon \quad \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Where α = EP-intercept
 EP = Employee Performance
 TS = Transactional Leadership Style
 $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Coefficients
 ϵ = Standard error of the estimate

LITERATURE REVIEW

Transactional Leadership Style

Transactional Leadership is a leadership style where the leader makes followers’ rewards contingent upon goal attainment. Transactional Leadership maintains the status quo (Bass, 1985), emphasizes results, stays within the existing structure of an organisation and measures success according to the organisation’s system of rewards and penalties (Iedu, 2020). Its focus is on attaining short-term goals. The main components of transactional leadership are contingent reward, active management by exception, and passive management by exception (Bass & Avolio, 1994).

Odumeru and Ogbonna (2013) indicated that there are two types of contingent reward - contingent positive reinforcement and contingent negative reinforcement. A transactional leader gives contingent positive reinforcement in the form of praise and rewards when goals are achieved on or before a scheduled time while a contingent negative reinforcement is given when goals are not met, tasks are not accomplished and performance falls below standard. Odumeru and Ogbonna (2013) also indicated that active management by exception means that the transactional leader anticipates problems, monitors the performance of followers, observes deviations from rules and regulations, and takes actions according to followers’ performance while passive management by exception means that the transactional leader does not get involved in attending to an issue if it is not severe.

Employee Performance

Employee performance refers to the results achieved from an employee’s effort while carrying out the duties and responsibilities associated with a job. Performance is the level of success a person achieves at a particular time in the process of carrying out tasks to meet targets that have been mutually agreed upon (Al Mehrzi & Singh 2016). Employee performance can be measured in financial or non-financial terms that reflect contribution to organisational effectiveness. Organisations such as food and beverages manufacturing companies aim at achieving goals through employees in order to improve and sustain their competitive positions in the marketplace. Gavrea (2011) indicated that performance is an important variable in management research because continuous performance leads to growth and progress in organisations.

Job Satisfaction

Job Satisfaction refers to feelings of contentment that a job position occupier derives by carrying out the duties and responsibilities of the job. Wicker (2011) defined job satisfaction as a sense of pride and inner fulfillment that results from performing a particular job. Gupta (2012) indicated that personal factors, social factors, cultural factors, and environmental factors affect job satisfaction. Variables that relate to personal factors include: education, experience, achievements, growth, responsibility, and personality. Social factors refer to relationship with co-workers, supervision, group work, prompt feedback from management, opportunity to participate in decision making, autonomy, empowerment and praise for efforts while cultural factors include: human resource management policies, leadership styles, exposure to training, technology and work organisation (Alromaihi et al., 2017). Variables that constitute environmental factors include: economic influences, governmental influences, technical influences, outer social influences, promotion, stress, salary and fringe benefits (Alromaihi et al., 2017).

Mediation Effect of Job Satisfaction

Studies that have reported the mediation effect of job satisfaction in the relationship between leadership styles and performance include: Halim (2021), Nanjundeswaraswamy (2021), and Widyatama (2021). A study by Halim et al. (2021) reported that job satisfaction fully mediated the relationship between transactional leadership and teachers' commitment in Malaysia. Nanjundeswaraswamy (2021) reported partial mediation of job satisfaction in the relationship between leadership styles including transactional leadership and the commitment of employees of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in India. Another study by Widyatama et al. (2021) on the mediating effect of job satisfaction in the relationship between leadership styles and employee performance indicated that job satisfaction did not mediate the relationship between transactional leadership and employee performance. The conclusion of the study was that in order to develop human resource leadership in the studied industry, more emphasis should be placed on transformational leadership style.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of this study is the expectancy theory proposed by Victor H. Vroom in 1964. The equation that defines the expectancy theory is given by: Motivation = Expectancy x Instrumentality x Valence (Goyal, 2015). Motivation refers to the extent an individual is energized or encouraged to expend effort on a job. Expectancy is a person's perception that effort would lead to performance. Instrumentality is a person's perception of the probability of receiving reward for expending effort. Valence refers to the perception of the magnitude and value of reward that would be associated with performance. The relevance of the expectancy theory stems from the relationship between employee motivation and job satisfaction as well as the relationship between job satisfaction and performance. A study by Kian et al. (2014) indicated that motivation had positive relationship with job satisfaction and that both had complementary relationship with other organisational variables. Fadlallah (2015) conducted a study on the impact of job satisfaction on employee performance and reported statistically significant positive relationship between job-satisfaction factors and performance. The results of these studies indicate that the role of organisational leadership in the process of supervising followers is to ensure that factors that result in employee motivation and promote job satisfaction are present in the workplace.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study was carried out based on a survey research design. Data were collected from a population of 1,460 employees of a food and beverage manufacturing company in Lagos State, Nigeria. The employees were randomly selected. The sample size was calculated from Taro Yamani formula, $n = N/(1+Ne^2)$, where n represents the sample size, N represents the population of study, and e is the error margin. With 5 percent error margin, the sample size, $n = 1,460/[1+1,460(0.05)^2] = 314$. Data analysis was based on 72 percent response rate. Regression analysis determined the effect of transactional leadership on employee performance while controlling for the mediator, job satisfaction. The conditions for mediation were verified based on Baron and Kenny's (1986) four-step approach. Baron and Kenny (1986) indicated that a variable can function as a mediator in causal relationships if regression analyses reveal that: the independent variable is a statistically significant predictor of the dependent variable; the independent variable is a statistically significant predictor of the mediator where the mediator serves as a dependent variable; the mediator is a statistically significant predictor of the dependent variable while controlling for the effect of the independent variable.

However, the following effect sizes were also obtained:

1. β_1 = Total effect of transactional leadership on employee performance.
2. β_2 = Direct effect of transactional leadership on job satisfaction.
3. β_3 = Direct effect of transactional leadership on employee performance.
4. β_4 = Direct effect of job satisfaction on employee performance while controlling for the effect of transactional leadership.

The indirect effect of transactional leadership on employee performance was obtained from equation (4). Equation (4) represents the product of the direct effect of transactional leadership on job satisfaction and the direct effect of job satisfaction on employee performance while controlling for the effect of transactional leadership.

$$\text{Indirect effect of transactional leadership on employee performance} = \beta_2 * \beta_4 \quad \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Regression Analysis of Transactional Leadership on Employee Performance

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.176	.053		3.330	.001
	Transactional Leadership	.945	.018	.962	52.677	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Author, 2024

It is shown in table 1 that transactional leadership significantly predicts employee performance ($\beta_1 = .945, t = 52.677, p < .05$). This leads to rejecting null hypothesis 1 at .05 significance level.

Table 2. Regression Analysis of Transactional Leadership on Job Satisfaction

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.385	.055		7.038	.000
	Transactional Leadership	.903	.019	.956	48.494	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

Source: Author, 2024

Table 2 indicates that transactional leadership significantly predicts job satisfaction ($\beta_2 = .903, t = 48.494, p < .05$). Therefore, null hypothesis 2 is rejected at .05 significance level.

Table 3. Regression Analysis of Transactional Leadership and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.170	.053		3.206	.002
	Transactional Leadership	.808	.121	.822	6.700	.000
	Job Satisfaction	.141	.122	.141	1.152	.251

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Author, 2024

It is shown in table 3 that the effect of transactional leadership on employee performance is statistically significant ($\beta_3 = .808$, $t = 6.700$, $p < .05$) and reduced with the inclusion of job satisfaction. This indicates that job satisfaction partially mediates the relationship between transactional leadership and employee performance. Therefore, null hypothesis 3 is rejected at .05 level of significance. Table 3 also indicates insignificant positive effect ($\beta_4 = .141$, $t = 1.152$, $p > .05$) of job satisfaction on performance.

Table 4. Effect Size

Effect	Direct	Indirect	Total
Transactional leadership on Job Satisfaction	.903	-	.903
Job Satisfaction on Performance	.141		.141
Transactional leadership on Performance	.808	.127	.945

Statistically significant effect ($p < .05$)

Source: Author, 2024

Table 4 indicates that transactional leadership produced the largest direct effect on job satisfaction followed by the direct effect of transactional leadership on employee performance.

CONCLUSION

Transactional leadership had potential to improve employee performance in the studied company. The results of this study gave indication that transactional leadership significantly predicted the employee performance and job satisfaction. The results also indicated a reduced and significant effect of transactional leadership on employee performance with the inclusion of job satisfaction as a mediating variable. This led to the conclusion that job satisfaction partially mediated the relationship between transactional leadership and employee performance. Job satisfaction produced insignificant positive effect on employee performance. These results produced evidence that employees were encouraged to expend effort on their jobs based on the rewards they received. They also signified the necessity for the management of the studied company to ensure the availability of factors that promote job satisfaction and to give more attention to the adequacy of rewards for attaining goals in a transactional relationship with employees as a means of boosting performance.

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Cite this Article: Ebuzoeme, F C (2025). Mediation Effect of Job Satisfaction between Transactional Leadership and Employee Performance. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 8(3), pp. 1497-1502. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i3-54>